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Abstract

Memory consolidation is a vital process that transforms new information into stable, long-term memories. Here, we discuss and compare 15 distinct theories and models of memory consolidation and its processes from a systems neuroscience perspective, as well as the role of sleep in relation to relevant memory consolidation models. Over decades of research on memory consolidation, hundreds of insightful papers have been produced with unique viewpoints, but not all of them have been analyzed in depth. We aim to summarize and compare these various theories of memory consolidation in an effort to bring disparate viewpoints into comparison. Each theory is provided with an explanation of its history and context, strengths and supporting evidence, weaknesses, limitations, and a general conclusion. All theories are divided into four categories based on their prevalence and amount of evidence, with an additional category devoted to sleep-related theories regardless of their reliability and recognition.

Keywords

Long-term memories, Short-term memories, Hippocampus, Consolidation

General Audience Summary

The process of consolidating new information into long-term memory is crucial for human intelligence and is known as memory consolidation. This review provides a thorough examination of 15 theories on memory consolidation, which aim to elucidate the mechanisms by which our brains store and retrieve memories, particularly during sleep. The paper discusses the importance of foundational theories in understanding memory, as well as commonly recognized modern views. It also explores newer theories that are supported by expanding data and examine sleep-related concepts that emphasize the significance of sleep in memory consolidation. The Multi-Store model is a fundamental hypothesis that explains the process by which information is transferred from sensory memory to short-term memory and eventually to long-term memory via rehearsal. Contemporary theories such as the Cognitive Schema Theory and Standard Model elucidate the organization and transmission of memory within specific brain regions. The Trace Transformation Theory and Competitive Trace Theory provide novel concepts on the mechanics of memory consolidation. The Two-Process Model of Sleep, which posits that sleep pressure enhances memory consolidation, is also examined. Overall, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of different perspectives on memory consolidation, with the aim of informing both researchers and professionals in the field. Certain theories are substantiated by empirical evidence, while others necessitate further investigation. Gaining insight into the process of memory consolidation enhances our comprehension of cognition and has the potential to aid in the treatment of memory issues.

Title: Comparison of Memory and Sleep Consolidation Theories: A Review of The Literature

The concept of memory consolidation was first mentioned in the writings of the famous Roman rhetoric teacher Marcus Fabius Quintilianus, dated in the first century AD (*Quintilian | Roman Rhetorician | Britannica*, 2023). He pointed to the "curious fact... that the interval of a single night will greatly increase the strength of the memory" and raised the possibility that "the power of recollection... undergoes a process of ripening and maturing during the time which intervenes" (*Quintilian, Institutio Oratoria, Book 11, Chapter 6, Section 43*, n.d.). These accounts show that human awareness of memory consolidation has existed for centuries.

It was not until significantly later when, in 1900 the term "consolidation" was proposed by the German researchers Müller and Alfons Pilzecker. Their study named this idea after the finding that memory requires time to fixate "Konsolidierung" (Müller, G. E., & Pilzecker, A., 1900). Sixty years later, a plethora of evidence for the concept of consolidation being a distinct process in memory formation was provided by the famous study of H.M. and other studies on retrograde amnesia (Scoville & Milner, 1957; Warrington, 1996). This acknowledgment permitted the further development of new memory theories that included memory consolidation as a process, which many consider the theoretical basis for memory research (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.; Bower, Gordon H., John B. Black, and Timothy J. Turner., 1979; Craik & Lockhart, 1972; McClelland et al., 1995; Melton, 1963; Squire & Alvarez, 1995a).

Categories of Theories

The theories discussed will be divided into four categories to improve comprehension of the paper. The first category is a theoretical baseline that provides and discusses theories that serve as theoretical foundations and are essential for understanding all subsequent theories. The next section will consist of general theories which are modern memory consolidation theories that are widely accepted and have substantial evidence. Newer theories of consolidation will be discussed next. These are more modern memory consolidation theories that are not yet well supported, and may lack sufficient evidence for their justification or lack thereof, but are still worth reviewing as they may provide a new perspective on the study of memory consolidation – for example, a possible neuroanatomical basis of engrams in MeshCODE theory (Goult, 2021). In addition, it is crucial to incorporate sleep-related theories of memory consolidation because sleep has a considerable impact on memory consolidation (Klinzing et al., 2019) and should therefore be discussed.

Theoretical Baseline

This section will introduce and discuss the substantial memory and memory consolidation theories that are currently widely considered as theoretical baseline knowledge. These theories are also essential to mention, as they provide a theoretical base for models discussed in further sections. For instance, the Multi-Store Model of Memory (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.) will be discussed here, which introduces the crucial concepts of short-term memory (STM) and long-term memory (LTM), upon which newer models, such as the Standard Model (Squire & Alvarez, 1995b) are built upon.

Theory of General Memory Processing

The most widely accepted theory that provides a basis for numerous models is the theory of the general memory process (Melton, 1963). It proposes that memory consists of three general cognitive processes: memory encoding, memory storage, and memory retrieval (Melton, 1963).

Encoding is defined as the process of receiving sensory input and transforming it into a form or a code that can be stored (i.e., memorization of information) (Craik & Lockhart, 1972; Melton, 1963). Information about something is encoded through one or more of these five methods: 1) visual encoding (i.e., appearance), 2) acoustic encoding (i.e., sound), 3) semantic encoding (i.e., fact or meaning), 4) tactile encoding (i.e., feeling), and 5) olfactory encoding (smell). Information about certain entities may be encoded in all five ways simultaneously. For example, a cat is warm (tactile encoding), has four legs (semantic encoding), meows (acoustic encoding), smells like a cat (olfactory encoding), and you can remember how exactly your cat looks (visual encoding) (Craik & Lockhart, 1972; Melton, 1963).

Storage is the next necessary process for memory formation. It refers to how, where, and for how long certain information can be remembered (Craik & Lockhart, 1972; Melton, 1963). Some memories, such as one's own parents' names, can be stored for nearly an unlimited amount of time, while some memories, such as what you ate for dinner two weeks ago, can only be stored for a short, limited duration. While information is typically encoded in one way, the form in which the same information is stored or retrieved may differ from its original, encoded form over time (McClelland et al., 1995). For example, if you meet someone for the first time, you might be able to recall an image of their look five minutes later (visual encoding). However, a week later, only certain facts about their appearance, such as "some yellow jackets," might be recalled (semantic).

Lastly, retrieval is defined as the process of accessing the encoded and stored information when it is needed (remembering) (Craik & Lockhart, 1972; Melton, 1963). Since the encoding and storage process is different for different information, the retrieval of such information is also thought to be different. Certain information can be recalled immediately, whereas other information takes up to a few seconds to be retrieved (Anderson & Pichert, 1978). Sometimes, an individual requires a connected piece of information about another entity (a clue) to retrieve information about the object of focus (Anderson & Pichert, 1978).

However, despite the wide acceptance that encoding, storage, and retrieval are the three main general memory processes, there are other components to consider, such as memory consolidation (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.; Craik & Lockhart, 1972; Frankland et al., 2004). The difference between encoding, storage, and retrieval compared to memory consolidation is that the former three have substantial credit in the scientific community and raise nearly no doubt about their reliability or existence (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.; Scoville & Milner, 1957; Wagner et al., 2001). These terms are widely used in scientific research and are thought of in modern university courses as factual processes rather than theoretical models. Thus, these terms will also be used in the writing of this paper for the sake of scientific specificity.

Multi-Store Model of Memory

It would take only a short while until new memory theories that included memory consolidation as a distinct process appeared. Thus, in 1968, Atkinson and Shiffrin developed the Multi-Store Model of Memory (MSM) (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.). The MSM states that there are three

unitary memory stores, between which information is transferred in a linear sequence. These three stores are sensory memory, short-term memory (STM), and long-term memory (LTM).

The model states that when information is read by sensory organs, it is first recorded in the sensory memory store. If an individual attends to the stimulus, the information is then transferred to the STM, and if the information is given meaning (elaborative rehearsal), it is then linearly allocated to the LTM (see Figure 1) (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.).

Figure 1. Visualization of the MSM processes and stores (*Multi Store Memory Model | Simply Psychology, n.d.*)

Thus, the idea of memory consolidation in this model is supported by the fact that there is a process (rehearsal) that helps the transfer of information from STM to LTM.

This model has gained sufficient recognition with the publication of the famous H.M. case study (Scoville & Milner, 1957) that will be discussed further in the manuscript, as the paper revealed prior unknown insights in the neurobiological basis of memory consolidation, specifically the involvement of the hippocampus in memory transfer from STM to LTM, which has significantly contributed to the recognition of the MSM (McClelland et al., 1995). Hence, it is appropriate to mention that MSM was built around sufficient scientific research done previously (“Anatomy And Physiology Of Memory,” 1958; Scoville & Milner, 1957)

The Levels of Processing Model

The Levels of Processing Model (LPM) is another memory model (Craik & Lockhart, 1972) that describes memory recall for stimuli as a function of the depth of mental processing. The LPM though acknowledges memory encoding, memory storage, and memory retrieval, describes the memory processes different from MSM, and serves a different viewpoint. According to this theory, there is only one type of memory, and the ability to remember depends on the depth of information processing (Craik & Lockhart, 1972). A deeper level of analysis produces a more sophisticated, longer-lasting, and more powerful memory trace than a shallow level of analysis. The processing depth is continuous from shallow to deep and may take any position between the extremes, as shown in Figure 2. Shallow processing leads to fragile memory trails that are prone to rapid decay (Craik & Lockhart, 1972). On the contrary, deep processing, such as semantic processing, causes more persistent memory traces. This model also classifies different types of processing as shown in Figure 2, but this is not essential for this paper and therefore will not be discussed.

Figure 2. LPM Visualized

The LPM directly contradicts the MSM. One major difference between the two models is that the MSM describes STM and LTM as two unitary stores, and information must pass through STM in order to eventually be stored in the LTM store (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.). The LPM does not distinguish between STM and LTM, but describes different levels of processing that represent a spectrum (from shallow to deeper) rather than distinct categories of memories (Craik & Lockhart, 1972). The deeper the processing, the easier it is to retrieve information. Another difference between the two memory models is that in the MSM, maintenance rehearsal occurs only within the STM store. However, the LPM asserts that two types of rehearsal occur at all levels of processing. Maintenance rehearsals that occur during shallow processing and elaboration rehearsals that are related to deeper processing (Craik & Lockhart, 1972).

However, it is important to mention that unlike the MSM with its highly credible neuroanatomical background, LPM fails to provide evidence from the biological field and is only mostly supported by cognitive studies (Eysenck, 1978), with the most recognized being Craik and Tulving's study on memory processing and retrieval (Craik & Tulving, 1975) which has gained criticism over the past years on aspects of low ecological validity and cause-effect relationship (Eysenck, 1978). This has led the LPM to lose its credibility, which has resulted in the rise of MSM being entitled as the most reliable.

All in all, these models build up the theoretical base that is necessary for an advanced understanding of memory consolidation. The vast majority of scientists in neuroscience, psychology, and psychiatry adhere to one of these models (Frankland et al., 2004; Haist et al., 2001; Nadel et al., 2000; Renner et al., 2012; Wagner et al., 2001). Although these models contradict each other, they all consider and allow for processes such as memory consolidation, which is the focus of this paper. That said, no matter which model is defined as the most reliable, any of these widely accepted models acknowledges the existence of memory consolidation, which permits the writing of this paper and allows a deeper dive into researching memory consolidation. Thus, the next section will attempt to explain memory consolidation from the system's point of view, providing general and widely accepted theories that are available to this day.

New vs. General Theories

In the previous section, it was stated that memories eventually undergo the process of consolidation to make them long-lasting and faster to remember. The models we covered attempt to explain memory and related processes from a systems neuroscience point of view, a subdiscipline of neuroscience that studies the function of neural circuits and systems (*Systems Neuroscience*, n.d.). In other words, while this process is somewhat understandable in terms of cognition, the biological reductionist point of view has not yet been explored, although certain attempts have previously been made (Joo & Frank, 2018; Squire et al., 2015). Additionally, due to various reasons such as the lack of reliable research and base theory on memory consolidation in other subdisciplines, as well as the core concept of memory consolidation being too broad for one paper (Roesler & McGaugh, 2019), it was decided to focus on memory consolidation theories only from a systems perspective. Although other subdisciplines are not less promising or insightful, at this point, the modern scientific community has simply gathered more information in the system subdiscipline, allowing the writing of a literature review (Joo & Frank, 2018).

Additionally, as was shown, all previously mentioned models of memories support the idea of memory consolidation (Atkinson & Shiffrin, n.d.; Craik & Lockhart, 1972), despite being different. Thus, since we considered theories that explain memory as a whole from a systems perspective, in the next sections, we will discuss different memory consolidation theories from the same system point of view (with some exceptions), split into two categories proposed by the author: general theories, modern memory consolidation theories that are widely supported, have sufficient evidence, and are pretty reliable; and new theories, modern memory consolidation theories that are not well supported, do not have enough evidence for their justification or disproof, but are still worth reviewing, as they may open another point of view in studying memory consolidation; for instance, the link between memory consolidation and types of learning (McClelland et al., 1995).

This paper delineates between established general theories and emerging new theories concerning memory consolidation. The purpose of this division is not to assert the superiority of one over the other, but rather to offer readers distinct perspectives for their consideration. General theories, while widely accepted, may lack definitive proof, whereas new theories provide alternative viewpoints for exploring memory consolidation. This categorization facilitates clarity and comprehension for readers seeking insight into the topic.

General Theories

In this section, general theories of memory consolidation from the systems' point of view will be discussed. Despite them being widely accepted theories and usually included in modern university syllabuses, these are still relevant for the paper in providing widely accepted views and ideas (i.e., the existence of STM and LTM) that founder the theoretical baseline upon which the further sections with more novel and complex models (i.e., The MeshCODE) will be built.

Cognitive Schema Theory

The first model in this section is the Cognitive Schema Theory (CST), which is a cognitive framework, proposed by J. Piaget, that explains how people utilize cognitive schemas, cognitive structures that help process, organize, and integrate information in the brain (Piaget,

1976). According to the CST, people construct cognitive schemas, organized units of information for an entity or event, through their experiences, and these schemas direct their perceptions, thoughts, and behaviors. According to the CST, humans interpret and make sense of the world around them using their cognitive schemas. These schemas, which resemble mental maps, help people classify and organize information in ways that ease memory retrieval and consolidation (Piaget, 1976).

The CST contends that a person's preexisting cognitive schemas — which direct the acquisition and retrieval of new information — have an impact on memory consolidation (Piaget, 1976). For instance, a person might have a schema for a "dog" that includes traits such as four legs, fur, and barking. This person will evaluate whether a new animal perceived in the future fits their schema for a dog when they come across one and compare its features to the ones of a dog. If the information matches the preexisting schema, that schema is activated, and hence the animal is mentally perceived as a dog, see Figure 3 below. Information about the animal ties to the preexisting schema, and if matches the cognitive representation of a dog (schema), will generate a cognitive "connection" that is thought to aid in memory structure and, consequently, memory consolidation (Piaget, 1976). It is also important to note that the cognitive schema is linked to sensory memory (i.e., the smell of the dog), episodic and semantic memories, and any cognitive representation of the 'dog' to evolutionary gain as fast and as precise recognition of a possible threat.

Figure 3. Visualization of the activation of the cognitive schema of the 'dog'. (Marc-Oliver, 2019)

Many studies have supported the CST. For instance, participants in one study were shown statements that were either compatible with or inconsistent with their schema for a certain issue (Bower, Gordon H., John B. Black, and Timothy J. Turner., 1979). The findings suggested that schemas play a significant role in information processing because individuals were quicker to understand and retain statements that fit their schema (Bower, Gordon H., John B. Black, and Timothy J. Turner., 1979). Another study furthered the understanding of the importance of schemas in memory retrieval (Anderson & Pichert, 1978). The story told to the participants had two possible interpretations depending on which schema was used. The next step was to ask the subjects to recall the incident from the primary or secondary schema. The findings

revealed that individuals were more likely to remember data that matched the activated schema, proving that schemas can affect how data are encoded and retrieved (Anderson & Pichert, 1978).

Furthermore, CST has been used in clinical contexts (Renner et al., 2012). For example, it is claimed that those who suffer from depression have unfavorable schemas that affect their ideas and actions. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) tries to assist people in identifying and altering these negative schemas to improve their mental health because they can result in inaccurate perceptions of the world (David et al., 2018).

Despite all of its applications, the CST has consistently come under fire (Thorndyke & Yekovich, 1980). The theory's lack of consideration for individual variations in cognitive schemas is one of its drawbacks. The theory makes the assumption that people have cognitive schemas that direct how they absorb information, but it does not explain why some people might have different schemas or why other people might not have fully formed schemas. The theory also fails to take into account how cognitive schemas may evolve with time as a result of new knowledge or experiences (Sadoski et al., 1991). The theory's inability to clearly explain how cognitive schemas are acquired is another drawback. The theory makes the supposition that people acquire cognitive schemas as a result of their interactions and experiences with the world, but it does not explain how this happens. Furthermore, the theory does not take into consideration how socioeconomic or cultural influences could affect how cognitive schemas emerge (Thorndyke & Yekovich, 1980). The application of CST to clinical populations is also constrained. Although the theory has been used to explain memory consolidation deficiencies in clinical groups, such as those with posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety disorders, or obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), it does not take into account the intricate psychological and physiological mechanisms that may be responsible for these abnormalities (Peeters et al., 2022). Furthermore, the theory might not adequately account for the variations in cognitive processes that can exist between individuals in clinical groups. Last but not least, the theory has come under fire for being overly general and lacking particular predictions that can be verified through empirical study. The theory, according to some academics, is too nebulous and lacks the clarity required to produce testable theories (Sadoski et al., 1991; Thorndyke & Yekovich, 1980).

In conclusion, the CST has limitations even if it has been useful in understanding cognitive processing and memory consolidation and has been supported by scientific research and time (Anderson & Pichert, 1978; Bower, Gordon H., John B. Black, and Timothy J. Turner., 1979). The theory may not adequately represent the complexity of clinical populations and does not fully account for individual variances in cognitive schemas. It also does not clearly explain how cognitive schemas are learned (Sadoski et al., 1991; Thorndyke & Yekovich, 1980). However, the theory offers a helpful framework for understanding how cognitive schemas might affect memory consolidation and has significant implications for the creation of interventions for clinical populations, especially those related to memory and its consolidation.

Standard Model

Another one of the earliest memory consolidation models is the Standard Model of Memory (SMM) (Squire & Alvarez, 1995b). The model states that STMs are initially encoded and stored in the hippocampus before gradually being transferred and consolidated to long-term storage in the neocortex and decaying from the hippocampus (Frankland & Bontempi, 2005).

The theory is also based on some assumptions about memory: 1) Information in short-term storage is in a state of activation. 2) "Permanent knowledge is activated as a byproduct of online cognitive processing and resides 'in' STM. STM is simply defined as the "collective set of this activated information in memory" (Nairne, 2002). 3) Currently activated information can be accessed immediately and effortlessly. 4) Activation is fragile and, without rehearsal, will not be maintained for long (Squire & Alvarez, 1995b). In this sense, activated memory is "a memory that is currently the focus of consciousness or was recently in awareness, as distinct from the vast body of stored memories that are currently inactive. Activation occurs through retrieval. According to one theory, an item in short-term or working memory is an item from long-term memory that has been activated." (*APA Dictionary of Psychology*, n.d.) Memory activation is the process of retrieving information from memory storage.

Memories are stored in the hippocampus for a day up to a week after initial learning, a hippocampus-dependent stage (Frankland & Bontempi, 2005). At this stage, the hippocampus is intensively "teaching" information to the cortex (mostly entorhinal cortex (EC)) (Basu & Siegelbaum, 2015). When information is retrieved, corticocortical synapses are strengthened, making memory independent of the hippocampus. Thus, starting one week after the first training experience, the memory is slowly consolidated to the neocortex, where it is permanently stored, thus supporting the multiple-store model since different memory stores will physically appear in different areas of the brain with corresponding neuroplasticity properties (Dudai, 2004). Later, hippocampal representations of new information will become active in explicit (conscious) recall or implicit (unconscious) recall, such as during sleep, which may explain the relationship between sleep and memory consolidation; however, this will be discussed more in the following sections (Dudai, 2004).

The hippocampus is believed to be able to store memories only temporarily because the hippocampal synapses are extremely dynamic and change quickly, whereas the neocortical synapses are less "flexible" and take time to rearrange, granting LTMs potentially unlimited storage (Belloso-Iguerategui et al., 2023). Thus, consolidation is the process in which the hippocampus continually activates the neocortex to create a strong connection between the two, as the standard model proposes.

Since the hippocampus can only temporarily support memories, it would be expected that the remaining activation would be seen only in the neocortex. Again, the famous H.M. case study (Scoville & Milner, 1957) can serve as evidence for the model's justification. First, during bilateral resection of the medial temporal lobe, the entire hippocampus of the patient was removed, which resulted in the inability to store any new memories after surgery for more than half an hour (anterograde amnesia), which corresponds to the STM; however, these memories could not be consolidated further into the LTM (Scoville & Milner, 1957). Such observations suggest that the hippocampus plays an essential, if not the main, role in memory consolidation. Additionally, the patient had partial retrograde amnesia, which means that he could not recall some memories that formed up to 3 years before surgery. Even important memories, such as an uncle's death, could not be recalled. However, without the hippocampus, memories could not be consolidated, suggesting its role as primary storage prior to transfer to the neocortex. If the functions of the hippocampus are impaired or removed, as happened in the case study, then the "bridge" between fully consolidated LTMs and consolidating STMs does not exist, and therefore the ability to remember for longer than the storage time of the STM is no longer possible. Squire and Alvarez also investigated the aspect of retrograde amnesia (Squire & Alvarez, 1995b). The researchers took the temporally graded nature of patients with retrograde amnesia as support for the model. They found that as soon as a connection has been established

within the neocortex, the hippocampus is no longer required. This process is dynamic and can last for several years, yet it supports the model and explains why some information on events that occurred up to 3 years before surgery in H.M.'s life (uncle's death) could not be retrieved (Belloso-Iguerategui et al., 2023; Squire et al., 2015). Thus, these memories were not consolidated and were still in the hippocampus-dependent stage, as the theory proposes.

On the other hand, a mirrored star tracing task that the patient had to do in the H.M. case study revealed that only long-term declarative (explicit) memory was affected. It turned out that the patient could still maintain and even ace particular motor skills without even remembering to do them. Such observations suggest that long-term nondeclarative (implicit) memories were still being consolidated and stored, even despite the absence of the hippocampus. Since the Standard Model does not distinguish between the memory types, generalizing all of them, such a limitation can be considered a contradiction, or at least a flaw, and leaves space for extension.

Additionally, the assumptions on which the model is based have been criticized in recent years. For example, there is evidence against the assumption of the Standard Model that information in STM is directly accessible (Nr.3). There is evidence produced by a group of researchers that is not consistent with this assumption (Tehan & Humphreys, 1996). They conducted a cognition experiment. They asked participants to remember the second of two blocks, and each block had four items. One of the first block variants could be "jail silk orange peach" and the second "page leap carrot witch". Participants were then asked to recall the vegetable from the second block and the type of juice from the second block; both questions were separated from each other (Tehan & Humphreys, 1996). The results showed that the participants had better STM for the "carrot" (critical item) when asked the first question rather than the second, which was represented by the likelihood that the critical item in the second block had been recalled in its correct serial position. According to the third assumption, "currently activated information can be accessed immediately and effortlessly", which was not the case in the experiment. The same item, depending on the question, was either recalled on time or, in the case of the second question, had a delayed recall (Tehan & Humphreys, 1996). This effect occurred because there was more interference from the words in the first block, as orange is also a type of juice. Thus, recall from STM depends on the nature of the retrieval cue, and information in STM is not always directly and effortlessly accessible, which does not correspond to the third assumption of the Standard Model.

Overall, the Standard Model is one of the most tested theories in memory consolidation. It has been maintained and supported for more than 20 years. The model has a strong theoretical base and a sufficient amount of evidence for its reliability (Dudai, 2004; Frankland et al., 2004; Scoville & Milner, 1957; Tehan & Humphreys, 1996). It also considers memory consolidation from the biological perspective, specifically the link between the hippocampus and the cortices, which has become a strong side, distinct from many other models (that is, CST). However, it also has enough criticism to raise doubts about some of the points of the model, such as memory activation (Kelley et al., 2018; Nairne, 2002; Scoville & Milner, 1957; Tehan & Humphreys, 1996). Furthermore, the theory itself is based on some assumptions, some of which do not seem to be true (Tehan & Humphreys, 1996). There is also the limitation that the theory does not distinguish between memory types (explicit and implicit), which in reality do not follow the same system consolidation (Scoville & Milner, 1957). Although the model has its strengths and strong evidence, there is still a lot of room for further research that could either justify or disprove it. Such topics could be a detailed test of the assumptions upon which the theory is based, the investigations of retrograde and anterograde amnesia, and differences in the process of memory consolidation in various types of memory.

Complementary Learning Systems Theory

McClelland's Complementary Learning Systems (CLS) theory is a generally established cognitive theory that describes how human memory works from a computational systems perspective (McClelland et al., 1995). This theory provides a computational explanation for system consolidation based on the advantages of linking complementary fast and slow learning systems (Blakeman & Mareschal, 2020). This theory posits that the brain contains two different learning systems, the hippocampus and the neocortex, which collaborate to develop and preserve memories. The hippocampus, which is in charge of STM, analyzes and consolidates new information before sending it to the neocortex, which maintains LTM (McClelland et al., 1995). The hippocampus is proposed to be specialized for episodic and declarative memory, allowing rapid learning and the encoding of new information. It plays a crucial role in initial memory formation. The neocortex, particularly the association areas, is believed to be responsible for the gradual integration of information from the hippocampus. This process results in the establishment of more stable and enduring memories. The theory posits that the collaboration between the hippocampus and the neocortex provides a flexible and adaptive learning system. This adaptability allows the brain to learn quickly from new experiences, while also building a repository of generalized knowledge.

While CLS theory has been lauded for its insights into human memory, it has also been condemned for oversimplifying memory's complexity. Some critics contend that memory is significantly more sophisticated than two systems that operate in tandem. For instance, Squire & Alvarez discovered that the hippocampus is involved in a wide variety of cognitive activities beyond memory, including spatial navigation and perceptual learning (1995). Therefore, it is doubtful that the hippocampus is primarily responsible for absorbing and consolidating new knowledge.

Furthermore, some researchers have argued that the distinction between STM and LTM is not as distinct as the CLS theory predicts. Instead, they claim that memory is a dynamic process involving a complex interaction between various brain regions and that the transfer of information from STM to LTM is not as straightforward as CLS theory suggests. For example, a study discovered that the prefrontal cortex, an area of the brain not normally linked to memory, is also important in the transfer of information from STM to LTM (Wagner et al., 2001), which does not align with the model.

In addition, while CLS theory has been lauded for offering a framework for comprehending how memory functions, some critics believe that it lacks adequate data to substantiate its assertions. One study (McClelland et al., 1995) determined that there was no evidence to support the assumption that the neocortex is entirely responsible for the storage of LTMs. They contend that the neocortex and hippocampal regions cooperate to store and retrieve memories, rather than working separately for STM and LTM. For example, one study holds that memories retaining contextual details (such as episodic memories) remain dependent on the hippocampus so long as they persist (Winocur & Moscovitch, 2011).

In spite of these objections, the CLS theory is supported by much evidence. For example, McClelland & Rogers indicated that individuals with hippocampal loss had trouble creating new LTMs, supporting the notion that the hippocampus is involved in the processing and consolidation of new information (2003). Furthermore, another study (Frankland et al., 2004) discovered that the neocortex can store LTMs independently of the hippocampus, indicating that the neocortex does play a role in LTM storage.

CLS also has major applications; CLS has consequences for understanding memory impairments and cognitive loss associated with aging. Recent research investigates how interruptions in complementary learning systems play a role in illnesses such as Alzheimer's disease and how treatment approaches can utilize this knowledge (Figueroa, n.d.). Computational models based on CLS principles are still being developed. Researchers are employing sophisticated simulations to evaluate and enhance the theoretical underpinnings of CLS. The purpose of these models is to provide an in-depth understanding of the functioning of complementary learning systems in intricate cognitive activities (Kumaran et al., 2016). CLS principles are applicable to educational neuroscience, a discipline that investigates the neurological processes involved in learning and education (Blakeman & Mareschal, 2020). Researchers may be using the findings of critical language studies findings to guide the development of teaching methods and curricular structure.

Hence, while CLS theory provides a valuable framework for comprehending how human memory functions, it has been challenged for oversimplifying memory's complexity and failing to give adequate data to back its claims (Squire & Alvarez, 1995b; Wagner et al., 2001). Yet, there is evidence to support the theory (Frankland et al., 2004; McClelland & Rogers, 2003) and it is probable that future studies will continue to deepen our understanding of how memory functions. Thus, it is essential to continue researching CLS theory, since it has the ability to shed light on the human brain's operations, provide insights into machine training and learning, and contribute to the cognitive understanding of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease.

Multiple Trace Theory

Multiple Trace Theory (MTT) was proposed as an alternative to the Standard Model (Nadel & Moscovitch, 1997). It states that whenever information is presented to a person, it is neurally encoded into a unique memory trace composed of a combination of specific attributes. Moreover, MTT builds on the distinction between semantic and episodic memory and addresses some limitations of the Standard Model with a focus on hippocampal dependence. Nadel and Moscovitch argued that it is necessary to distinguish between semantic and episodic memory when studying memory consolidation, as they rely on two different memory systems (Bernard et al., 2004). When episodic information is encoded, there are semantic aspects of that specific memory that will be encoded in addition, such as the time of the event, the venue, or the number of people in the event and their names. This is proposed as an explanation for the varying gradients of memory loss seen in amnesic patients (Nadel & Moscovitch, 1997).

Thus, the retrieval of episodic (and spatial) memories is claimed to always depend on medial temporal lobe (MTL) structures, including the hippocampus. MTT states that both episodic and semantic memories are based on the hippocampus, but semantic memories become somewhat independent of the hippocampus during consolidation. Semantic memories are thought to be only formatted and consolidated by the hippocampus (Moscovitch et al., 2006), whereas remote memories for such information (e.g., names of people and places) are thought to be operated independently of the hippocampus (Nadel et al., 2000). Moreover, amnesic patients with hippocampal damage show some traces of memory, which, although used to support the Standard Model, also suggests that memory is stored outside the hippocampal system (Nadel & Moscovitch, 1997). Nadel and Moscovitch argue that these retained memories lost their richness of experience over time and exist only as semantically depersonalized memories. However, they claim that such observations support their idea that episodic memories are highly dependent on the hippocampal system, but semantic memories are established elsewhere

in the brain and can survive hippocampal damage (i.e., lesion or seizure) (Nadel & Moscovitch, 1997). Such an allocation, from an evolutionary point of view, would minimize memory loss due to injury or a stroke, thus enhancing the survivability of a species, which sounds plausible, although has not been proven certain. In this way, Nadel and Moscovitch see memory hippocampal independence as an evolutionary benefit.

An important difference between the MTT and the SMM is that the Standard Model proposes that after a certain period of time (i.e., a few years), all memories become independent of the hippocampus. However, Nadel and Moscovitch showed in their study that the hippocampus is involved in the recall of all remote autobiographical memories, regardless of their storage time (Nadel & Moscovitch, 1997). An important point to interpret their results is that activation was equally strong in the hippocampus and MTL, even though the information retrieved was encoded up to 45 years prior to the date of the experiment. This is complicated by the fact that the hippocampus is constantly involved in encoding new information (memories), and activation is difficult to isolate with baseline measurements due to this fact (McClelland & Rogers, 2003). Thus, hippocampal activation in remote memory retrieval may be just a byproduct of the subject encoding the experiment as an event. However, Nadel and Moscovitch have not provided a sufficient explanation of why the hippocampus might be activated during retrieval, which remains a crucial uncertainty in the theory and a possible limitation of the explanation provided by the authors.

However, a research team (Haist et al., 2001) sought to examine the temporal nature of memory consolidation within the hippocampus to test the interpretation of Nadel and Moscovitch. They found that a few years after encoding, the hippocampus did not contribute significantly to the recollection of distant memories. They state that the development of more accurate functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) at some point allowed to distinguish between the hippocampus and the entorhinal cortex, which, according to them, is more lasting in its activation from remote memory retrieval. Another aspect of the experiment done by Nadel and Moscovitch that they criticize is the use of memories during testing, which is not accurate as memories are flexible and prone to bias (e.g., leading questions). Moreover, they claim that the initial interview on the scanner by Nadel and Moscovitch acted as an encoding event, since such differences between recent and distant memories would be obscured.

As stated above, there is evidence that cortical bound traces are semantic and relatively context-free, whereas hippocampal bound traces are contextual and rich in spatial and temporal aspects. Thus, the hippocampus is not required in the recall of distant semantic memories; however, the retrieval of distant episodic memories always must, regardless of the memory's duration. The role of the hippocampus in the retrieval of semantic and episodic memories has been the main controversy between MTT and SMM. In reality, this is the only prediction that has been consistently testable for either theory to date, although evidence for even this prediction has been at best flimsy. Both models were presented to explain amnesia data from human and animal investigations, specifically the apparent retrograde amnesia (RA) gradient (Nadel & Moscovitch, 1997; Scoville & Milner, 1957). In many instances, the RA gradient was flat and, in some instances, the degree of the RA gradient depended on the extent of the lesion (Frankland & Bontempi, 2005). However, with advances in fMRI, a new approach to the debate was introduced. Nadel and Moscovitch demonstrated that medial temporal fMRI activity is equally predictive of recollection of current and distant memories. As Yassa and Reagh (2013) mentioned, "However, a major criticism of these studies is that the hippocampus is involved in incidental and automatic encoding during retrieval tasks, which may obscure retrieval-related activity (Buckner et al., 2008; Haist et al., 2001; M. A. Yassa & Reagh, 2013). A relatively

recent survey of evidence-based amnesia studies in rodents with partial and complete hippocampal damage provides overwhelming support for flat RA gradients, arguing against SMM (Sutherland et al., 2010). Importantly, however, these data points also argue against one prediction of MTT, which is that partial hippocampal damage will lead to a temporal RA gradient. Thus, neither model can adequately account for lesion data in animals."

Thus, Multiple trace theory is an innovative concept that opens up a new perspective on memory consolidation and the role of the hippocampus within it. The discovery that RA was often not temporally graded was anchored in a testable theoretical framework, which added some reliability to the theory. Although much of the relevant literature on rodents can be interpreted as supporting MTT (Bernard et al., 2004; Frankland & Bontempi, 2005; Moscovitch et al., 2006), specific tests of core predictions regarding the effects of partial and complete hippocampal damage, the effects on context-specific versus independent memories, and the expansion of hippocampal memory traces in physiological recordings and IEG activation patterns have not been supported by a consistent body of evidence (Buckner et al., 2008; Haist et al., 2001; Sutherland et al., 2010; M. A. Yassa & Reagh, 2013). Thus, like SMM, MTT has a number of evidence and counter-evidence studies. However, for complete justification or disproof of the theory, there is still a lot of research needed. For further research that could justify or disprove it, topics on retrograde and anterograde amnesia, the entorhinal cortex, and the medial temporal lobe are needed.

Thus, both models require refinement and theoretical adjustment given their reliance on somewhat outdated fMRI and mice experiment data, as discussed earlier. Consequently, certain aspects, such as RA gradients and hippocampal dependence on LTM, remain ambiguous. Despite both models offering empirical support for their assertions on these issues, they have faced significant critique, raising doubts about their reliability. Consequently, the debate between SMM and MTT continues as a fundamental scholarly discourse until new advances in memory systemization emerge. Until then, it is the personal choice of the readers to engage in critical evaluation on their own or propose alternative perspectives to the ones aforementioned.

New Theories

After describing some well-recognized memory consolidation models, this paper now delves into discussing newer theories that may not have received enough attention (yet). Even classical models, such as SMM and MTT, have enough criticism and theoretical flaws that are sometimes neglected by biased members of the scientific community. At this point, I would like to refer to Max Planck's principle, which states that 'a new scientific truth does not triumph by convincing its opponents and making them see the light, but rather because its opponents eventually die and a new generation grows up that is familiar with it'. (Planck, 1950). Considering such an assertion, it is almost vital to view some other perspectives that may not be as concrete as the models explained above. Thus, despite the fact that the theories stated in this section may not have much scientific evidence and, at the same time, counterevidence or criticism, it is still important to discuss them in order to maintain academic objectivity. The main purpose of this review of the literature is to exactly collect and analyze theories of memory consolidation, even if the author subjectively does not agree with them. Therefore, this section may be critical to providing alternative views; however, reliability and theory analysis may not be the main focus of this section, at least for some theories.

Due to the fact that the models in this section are novel, it is essential to point out that there is a possibility that entire paragraphs may be devoid of references. This is because the authors

themselves may be the only source of information. One example is the MeshCODE theory, published in 2021. Since it was published so recently, it has a relatively low reference score and no sufficient information from other sources. In light of this, I would like to state that if there is a certain paragraph within this section that does not contain references, you should refer to the original publication of that particular model stated at the beginning of the model description.

Trace Transformation Theory

The first theory to be examined within this section is Trace Transformation Theory (TTT), which is a cognitive theory that has garnered a great deal of attention from scholars and scientists in recent years (Sekeres et al., 2018). TTT proposes that as people get older and gain more life experience, their detailed, episodic (context-specific) memories gradually transform into forms of the original that lack context specificity and detail, but maintain the gist and schematic elements (TTT is based on the notion of Schema theory) (Sekeres et al., 2018). TTT provides a novel approach for memory consolidation by positing that experiences (including episodic memories) are not just transferred from the hippocampus to the neocortex but rather changed within the hippocampus itself from short-term perceptually rich episodic memories into long-term generalized and often semantic memories (memory consolidation) and only then transferred to different parts of the neocortex, where transformed memories become hippocampus independent. Such memories are transformed from a detail-rich and context-specific memory into a generalized form (a “trace”) of that memory that can be integrated with other stored information in the neocortex (Sekeres et al., 2018).

The theory also distinguishes between the anterior and posterior hippocampi, stating their distinct roles in memory consolidation and memory transfer. This is important as no other previous model has made clear distinctions between the roles of different hippocampal regions within the process of memory consolidation.

According to the model, episodic memories consist of details, gist, and schemas. The hippocampus plays a central role in representing episodic memories, with different regions within it responsible for different aspects. The posterior hippocampus (pHPC) interacts with the neocortex to represent detailed perceptual information, while the anterior hippocampus (aHPC) represents the gist of memories through its interaction with the neocortex and the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC), which mediates schemas. As memories age, there is a shift from pHPC to aHPC, and eventually to the mPFC. If only schemas remain, memories are mediated solely by the mPFC without hippocampal involvement. The model suggests that cueing can help recover lost information in healthy individuals but not in patients with relevant brain damage. Damage to the mPFC impairs memory retrieval due to its role in schema instantiation and strategic processes.

The model also highlights the dynamic interaction and coexistence of memory components mediated by different brain structures. The entorhinal cortex and thalamic nucleus reuniens are mentioned as important for relaying information and coordinating activity between the hippocampus and the mPFC. The formation and transformation of memories involve various factors and pathways that require further investigation, according to the authors. Therefore, the size and location of hippocampal lesions can have different effects on memory, which emphasizes the importance of considering regional specialization. The time course for memory transformation and the transition to hippocampal independence are still poorly understood.

Some memories may become semantic or schematic independently of the hippocampus through fast mapping mediated by the perirhinal cortex.

However, the concepts of details, gist, and schemas require further refinement and consensus in their definitions. Different forms of transformation may rely on different mechanisms and structures. Despite important advances, much remains to be learned about the neural basis of memory transformation, considering the involvement of other regions of the brain and the transformation of temporal and sequential information. In addition, TTT has faced criticism for disregarding specific aspects of memory consolidation. The explanation for the differential susceptibility of certain memories to forgetting remains unaddressed. The TTT model fails to consider the influence of sleep on memory consolidation, despite evidence indicating its notable role in this process (Ackermann & Rasch, 2014). Although none of the previous models have had any references to the role of sleep in memory consolidation, during the publication of the above-mentioned, this link between sleep and memory was not as evident as it is now. Therefore, it can be argued that TTT does not offer a comprehensive perspective on all aspects of memory consolidation despite the recent knowledge gained in this field. Instead, it primarily focuses on the mechanism of memory consolidation and the transition from the hippocampus to the cortices. Although the proposed theoretical framework, TTT, can serve as a basis for future research in narrowing the gaps in our understanding of memory transformation and consolidation, it is worth noting that, now, considering its novelty, TTT has certain theoretical uncertainties within its foundation.

The theory in question, having been published and revised within the last decade, has yet to receive substantial critique from the scientific community or undergo the test of time. In particular, no significant contradictory evidence has emerged in recent years to warrant questioning of the theory. From one perspective, it signifies that the information is current and adheres to contemporary understanding. On the contrary, the theory of TTT lacks sufficient reliability due to the inadequate research conducted to evaluate its validity. Sekere et al. attempted to assess their model by delineating its strengths and limitations, as well as citing prior corroborative research conducted on both human and animal subjects. The present paper refrains from presenting the objections of the individuals in question, as doing so would be a mere repetition of their statements, which can simply be accessed in their paper (Sekeres et al., 2018).

Consequently, while TTT has been challenged for lacking adequate data to support its assertions and for ignoring certain aspects of memory consolidation, it provides a unique perspective on how the brain organizes and consolidates memories. TTT suggests that memories are modified within the hippocampus and that this transformation process involves a complex interaction between the hippocampus and cortices. Most notably, TTT provides an in-depth explanation of how memories are processed in the brain and what the associated regions are. This attention to detail and neuroanatomy is the main strength of the model as it attempts to use recent findings in its claims. Although additional research is necessary to properly comprehend the role of the hippocampus in memory consolidation (to which the authors agree), TTT has the potential to reveal vital insights into the human brain's operations and, of major importance, set the standard of cognitive model in-depth description and dimensionality, not being limited to so-called baseline knowledge, but rather trying to consider recent findings.

Competitive Trace Theory

Another cognitive theory known as Competitive Trace Theory (CTT) has recently attracted much attention from academics and scientists. CTT is a theoretical framework in cognitive neuroscience and psychology that aims to explain how the brain processes and stores episodic memories (M. Yassa & Reagh, 2013). By indicating that memories compete with each other for access to limited brain resources, CTT suggests a novel method of memory consolidation in which the strongest memories are kept and the weakest ones are lost. According to CTT, several brain pathways are activated simultaneously when we experience something. The "winner," or the pathway that is the strongest, is the only one that is preserved as a memory because not all paths are equally powerful. Competitive learning is the name given to this process (M. Yassa & Reagh, 2013).

CTT is influenced by the concept of MTT that older memories are linked to a higher number of retrievals compared to current memories, resulting in increased neural representations in the hippocampus and neocortex. Yassa and Reagh (2013) propose that each time a memory is recalled, it is done in a different context, resulting in the incorporation of both old and new elements into the memory. This is known as recontextualization. Pattern separation in the hippocampus enables unique representations of each version, but in the neocortex, the versions overlap, causing competitive interference. Only overlapping components in the neocortex are preserved, allowing for the gradual development of semantic memories or schemas, as suggested by CLS and MTT. Veridical episodic information is only accessible for recent recollections. Older memories are simplified versions of the original stored in the neocortex or modified versions of the original that rely on the hippocampus, but contain misleading elements that become more prominent as the memory ages. Remote memories may not usually contain more illusory features than recent ones. The quantity and vividness of memories decrease over time, but accuracy tends to stay high, sometimes above 90%, even for long periods of time, as supported by MTT (Diamond et al., 2020; Evans & Fisher, 2011). Evidence on the impact of repeated retrievals or retrieval practice on memory typically does not result in competitive interference and memory deterioration. Retrieval practice, in line with MTT, generally enhances memory for both episodic and semantic aspects relative to memories that have not been recalled or have been restudied.

Furthermore, according to CTT, memories are dispersed across many brain regions rather than being kept in one place. When we retrieve a memory, the several areas that house its information are simultaneously reactivated, enabling us to recall the memory. The role of interference in memory development and retrieval is a crucial component of CTT. Similar memories clash for the same brain pathways, causing interference that makes it challenging to remember a particular memory. This may cause memory loss or mixing of memories. It has implications for understanding how we learn and retain information and has been used in a variety of domains, including psychology, neuroscience, and education (Darby & Sloutsky, 2015).

Therefore, the central claims of CTT are: “1) Every time a memory is reactivated, the hippocampus recontextualizes the memory by re-encoding a similar but not identical memory trace that is stored using associative connectivity between the hippocampus and the neocortex. 2) Memories are decontextualized over time by competitive interference among these similar but not identical multiple memory traces. This simultaneously leads to the consolidation of semantic memory in the neocortex and the loss of episodic details. 3) Veridical episodic details are only available in very recent memories. As memories age, these details are replaced by

recontextualized details stored by the hippocampus that give rise to illusory memories that become more prevalent as the age of the memory increases. In other words, recent episodic and remote episodic memories vary in accuracy of details and strength of semantic content.” (M. Yassa & Reagh, 2013)

Although CTT has received support and recognition, it has also come under fire for lacking adequate evidence to back up its claims and for failing to take some components of memory consolidation into account. The absence of proof to back up CTT's assertions is one of its key complaints. For example, one study (Davis et al., 2021) discovered that certain individuals could recognize images they had previously viewed even if they did not explicitly remember them. In contrast to CTT's assertion that only the strongest memories are maintained, this implies that memories can be retained even if they are not the strongest. It is crucial to take into account CTT's limitations and the research that refutes its findings. Additionally, CTT has come under fire for not taking into account several components of memory consolidation. For example, it does not take into account the importance of sleep in memory consolidation, which has been demonstrated to be crucial for memory consolidation (yet, the model was published after the sleep-memory link was discovered). Furthermore, CTT does not clearly explain why some memories are emotionally more intense than others, which is crucial for memory consolidation as it could provide information on memory loss from PTSD or fear conditioning. Thus, CTT might not give a whole picture of memory consolidation, but is still a tremendous model.

Notwithstanding these objections, the CTT is also supported by evidence. The theory that memories fight for access to cerebral resources is supported, for instance, by one study (Miller & Desimone, 1994), which demonstrated that neuronal activity in the monkey brain was strongest for the attended stimulus and weakest for the unattended stimulus. The idea that memories are actively consolidated and that they can be lost if they are not strong enough is further supported by another study (Nadel et al., 2000) that discovered that preventing the reconsolidation of memory can result in the loss of the memory. CTT provides a distinctive view on how the brain organizes and consolidates memories. According to theory, memories compete with each other for access to scarce cerebral resources and, as a result of this competition, the stronger memories are kept while the weaker ones are lost. Compared to other theories that only consider the transfer or modification of memories, the CTT provides a more nuanced picture of memory consolidation by emphasizing the rivalry between memories and the intermemory relationship, implying a clear hierarchy of retrieval. Additionally, CTT may be able to explain some events that are challenging to understand in terms of other theories. For example, CTT may contribute to understanding why some memories are more resistant to forgetting than others, since more powerful memories would have prevailed in the fight for brain resources. Weaker memories can eventually lose competition for cerebral resources, according to CTT, which may help explain why some memories can be lost over time.

In summary, CTT presents a novel point of view on memory processing and consolidation within the brain. However, it has faced criticism for not having sufficient empirical support and overlooking certain aspects of memory consolidation, despite garnering notable support. Although a deeper exploration is necessary to fully grasp the extent of competition in memory consolidation, CTT holds promise in shedding light on the intricacies of human brain function.

MeshCODE Theory

The MeshCODE theory is a new cognitive theory (Goult, 2021), which states that memory is organized based on a hierarchical network of categories, with more general categories at the top and more specific categories at the bottom. Each concept is represented by a unique code, which includes the codes of its parent categories, forming a MESH (Memory, Encoding, and Storage Hierarchy) code. For example, the concept of a "dog" would be represented by a code that includes the codes for "animal," "mammal," and "canine." (Goult, 2021)

According to the MeshCODE theory, memory retrieval is facilitated by the similarity between the cues used to retrieve a memory and the codes used to store that memory. The more similar the cues and codes, the more easily memory can be retrieved. Furthermore, the theory suggests that memory is stored not only in the brain but also in the environment. This is because our environment often provides cues that help us retrieve memories. For example, seeing a specific location may trigger memories of past experiences that took place in that location (Metzger, 2002).

Several studies have been conducted that test the validity of MeshCODE theory directly or indirectly. For example, a study investigated the effect of hierarchical organization on memory performance (Naim et al., 2019). Participants were presented with lists of words that were organized hierarchically or randomly. Hierarchical lists consisted of words that were grouped into categories, with more general categories at the top and more specific categories at the bottom. The randomly organized lists consisted of words that were presented in no particular order. The results showed that the participants remembered significantly more words from the hierarchical lists than from the randomly organized lists, supporting the idea that hierarchical organization facilitates memory performance.

Another study investigated the same topic (Bower et al., 1969). The researchers presented participants with categorized word lists and manipulated the depth of the category hierarchy. In one condition, the lists were organized into a shallow hierarchy with a few levels of subcategories, and in another condition, the lists were organized into a deep hierarchy with many levels of subcategories. The results of the study showed that participants recalled more words from the lists organized in the deep hierarchy than from those organized in the shallow hierarchy. Furthermore, participants were faster in recalling words from deep hierarchy lists, indicating that the hierarchical structure facilitated the retrieval of information from memory. The study suggests that hierarchical retrieval schemes can help memory recall by providing a more efficient and effective means of accessing stored information.

The article "Environmental Context and Human Memory" by Steven M. Smith and Arthur Glenberg discusses the role of environmental context in human memory. The authors propose that context provides important cues for memory retrieval and that the way information is encoded in a particular context can have a significant impact on memory performance. The article presents several studies that demonstrate the effects of environmental context on memory. One study found that participants who learned information in a particular context were better able to recall that information when tested in the same context, compared to when they were tested in a different context (Abernethy, 1940). Another study showed that changes in context can cause forgetting of previously learned information, suggesting that environmental context plays an important role in memory consolidation (Thomson, 1972).

You might have noticed that MeshCODE theory does not provide a specific account of memory consolidation itself. However, the theory suggests that memory storage is a dynamic process that involves an ongoing interaction between different components of the memory system. According to MeshCODE theory, memory is encoded through the formation of connections between neurons in the brain. These connections are strengthened over time through a process called long-term potentiation (LTP), which is thought to be a key mechanism of memory consolidation. As these connections become stronger, the memory is stored more securely and can be retrieved more easily. The theory also suggests that memory retrieval is an active process that involves the reconstruction of information from various sources. This means that memories are not simply "replayed" from storage, but are instead reconstructed in response to retrieval cues. This retrieval and reconstruction process can also contribute to memory consolidation, as the act of retrieving information can strengthen the connections between neurons in the brain.

Although the model establishes a connection to the intermemory hierarchy and elucidates the influence of environmental cues on recall, MeshCODE theory has garnered considerable interest by positing the existence of engrams, which are cognitive information units embedded in a physical substrate or memory's physical units. This assertion holds significance given the longstanding debate surrounding the origins of memory. (Camina & Güell, 2017). The MeshCODE theory suggests that the network of talin and vinculin molecules (mechanosensitive proteins that are recruited early to integrin-based nascent adhesions (NAs) (Han et al., 2021)) supporting the synaptic connections serves as an advanced mechanical computing and memory system (Goult, 2021). Mechanical memory involves the precise transmission of mechanical impulses between neurons through distinct synaptic connections that are separate from the main cell body.

The talin rod area consists of 13 switch domains, R1–R13 (Goult et al., 2013). The switch domains referred to are helical bundles that exhibit opening and closing behavior in reaction to mechanical signals (Yao et al., 2016). The switches regulate signaling outputs by enlisting and replacing various signaling molecules based on their condition (Goult, 2021). When unbound, one state of the 13 talin switches reveals nine binding sites for vinculin (Gingras et al., 2005). Vinculin stabilizes the 1 state of the talin switch it is bound to, coordinates signaling through its helical bundles, and interacts with actin to create more cytoskeletal connections and structural support. The switch patterns and signaling complexes that form allow information to be transmitted over time and altered by slight variations in mechanical force. When a signal triggers synaptic release, it activates the cell's motors at that specific synapse. According to the MeshCODE theory, this localized force generation changes the patterns of 1's and 0's in the talin molecules on both sides of the stimulated junction, affecting the resulting signaling outputs, see Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Talin is essential to memory formation. (A) It has an N-terminal FERM domain for integrin binding and 13 helical bundles for the talin rod domains R1-R13. Each talin helical bundle has a mechanical binary switch mechanism that switches between folded “0” and unfolded “1” states under mechanical tension. Three-rod domains change from 000 to 010 during cytoskeletal force spikes. (D) A binary string talin molecule with nine vinculin binding sites (green labels) switches dynamically: At rest, all 13-rod domains are folded “0”; (ii) talin is tethered between integrin: ECM and F-actin, adopting a specific switch pattern on adhesion; (iii) Two contractility spikes trigger switches (iii and iv), while reduced contractility resets one switch to 0 (v). System dynamics determine the sequence and switch state. (Goult, 2021)

This concept is supported by studies conducted by Kneussel and Wagner in 2013, and Bagci et al. in 2020 (Bagci et al., 2020; Kneussel & Wagner, 2013). The hypothesis suggests that the cytoskeletal structure of cells functions as a mechanical system that combines all MeshCODEs within the cell, connecting with cell-cell junctions, organelles, and the nucleus. Local changes in the coding at a synapse impact the global mechanical homeostasis computation of the neuron by resolving internal interdependencies inside the cell using updated patterns. Once equilibrium is achieved, the arrangement of 1's and 0's within the cell changes, and the entire cytoskeletal apparatus is refreshed. Hence, the model implies that the interactions between talin and vinculin molecules founder the molecular origin of human memories (engrams), assessing this mechanical system to be similar to those of computer bits (0's and 1's).

Current models of cytoskeletal connections lack accurate scaling, hindering the understanding of how changes in the geometries of talin "memory" molecules could influence synaptic signaling. One study conducted an in-depth structural examination of the molecules in the MeshCODE complexes to create accurate models of the complexes mediated by talin (Barnett & Goult, 2022). Modeling the mechanical positioning of molecules within a synapse, the study suggests that each molecule interacting with MeshCODE would have a specific location in 3D space determined by switch patterns, resembling a 3D Venn diagram. By changing the switch patterns, the physical closeness of enzymes to their substrates changes, which in turn affects enzymatic activity. The rearrangement of molecules within a confined space, mostly in one dimension, is similar to a car's gearbox and reveals a method by which binary information might regulate synaptic transmission, the authors claim.

However, while the MeshCODE theory has received impressive support from several studies, it is not without its limitations and criticisms. One criticism of the theory is that it does not account for the role of emotions, attention, and other cognitive factors, such as sleep. Emotional experiences are often remembered more vividly and with greater detail than neutral experiences, and the MeshCODE theory does not explain how emotions are encoded and stored in memory. Since Benjamin T. Goult (the model's author) asserts a biological origin of engrams, it would be "strong" to pinpoint the link between sleep-induced metabolic changes and their effects on talin and vinculin. Another criticism is that the theory assumes a linear sequence of memory processing stages, which some researchers argue is too simplistic to accurately reflect the complexities of the brain (Nadel & Hardt, 2011).

Overall, the MESH theory has been influential in shaping the field of memory research, especially in discussing and offering the biological origin of engrams (talin and vinculin). This is the most impressive aspect of the model as no other models within this paper have made such claims. The model does have consistent reliability from certain studies (Abernethy, 1940; Barnett & Goult, 2022; Naim et al., 2019; Thomson, 1972; Yao et al., 2016), but it has also been subject to some criticism, especially pointing out its limitations such as emotion and attention influence or the assumption of a linear sequence of memory processing stages. Additionally, it seems that not many have taken this model seriously (or at least not yet) since it appears that Benjamin T. Goult is the only one publishing serious inroads regarding his model, often citing his own publications. Although such dedication is admirable, there is a risk of research and confirmation biases. Moreover, the MeshCODE theory does not provide a specific account of memory consolidation, which is important within this paper; however, it does suggest that memory storage and retrieval are dynamic processes that involve ongoing interaction between different components of the memory system. This view of memory is consistent with current research on memory consolidation. To this day, researchers continue to explore and refine the MeshCODE theory in order to better understand the complexities of memory consolidation processes.

The Global Workspace Theory

The last model within this section is the Global Workspace Theory (GWT). Bernard Baars and Stan Franklin offered a paradigm for understanding consciousness in 1982 (Baars, 2005). It was designed to effectively consider a wide range of matched conscious and unconscious processes. GWT has played a significant role in conceptualizing consciousness and higher-order cognition as arising from competition and integrated information flows across extensive, parallel brain processes.

At this point, it is important to outline that the model is not as novel as the previous ones within this section and does not elaborate extensively on memory consolidation; it rather attempts to explain how human consciousness works. Hence, only the memory part will be discussed in detail, and the theory will not be as strictly assessed, taking into consideration its main focus and publication date. The rationale behind placing this model here is that, although it was published a few decades ago, the main contributions and recognition this model gained within the past 20 years, following several updates and republishing (i.e., in 2005). Thus, only the newest edits and corrections will be discussed.

The model aims to explain how awareness (conscious perception) develops within the brain. Since Bernard Baars and colleagues first introduced it in 1982 and then updated it in 1993 and 2005, it has gained popularity as a framework for comprehending a range of cognitive processes, including memory consolidation. The GWT's central hypothesis is that consciousness develops as a result of the integration of data from several specialized processing units that are dispersed throughout the brain, creating the so-called "global workspace". These modules are in charge of processing various sensory data as well as higher-order cognitive functions like attention, planning, and decision-making. Yet, they usually work separately from one another and are unaware. The "global workspace" notion, which refers to a dispersed network of brain areas engaged in conscious awareness and attention, is the foundation of the GWT. The theory holds that the global workspace serves as a focal point or bottleneck for information processing, enabling the sharing and fusion of data from various processing modules. Once information is brought into awareness and made available for additional processing, this integration process is what gives rise to conscious experience (Baars, 2005).

One area where the GWT has been successfully used is memory consolidation (Baars, 2005). The theory has been used in particular to explain how data is moved during consolidation from STM to LTM. According to the GWT, the prefrontal cortex and parietal cortex are two examples of specialized brain regions where STM is largely processed. These modules are in charge of short-term information storage and manipulation, but they rarely result in long-term adjustments to neural connections. The input information must be included in the global workspace so that it may be accessed and used by a greater variety of neural networks before it can be sent to LTM. The hippocampus, a part of the brain that is important for the generation and retrieval of LTMs, is assumed to be involved in this integration process. The hippocampus is believed to serve as a bottleneck or gateway for the flow of information, allowing the integration of pertinent information into the overall workspace while excluding irrelevant or distracting information.

The theory has flaws and has been criticized for not clearly defining the process by which information is chosen and integrated into the global workspace. For instance, some studies have proposed that other aspects, such as motivation and emotion (i.e., fear memory), may also play a role in determining which information is selected and may not just be limited to attention (Izquierdo et al., 2016). The GWT's inability to explain how information is processed unconsciously is another flaw in the theory. Although the theory claims that consciousness develops as a result of the information being integrated into the global workspace, it is not obvious how this process can explain the numerous cognitive processes that take place without conscious awareness, including memory consolidation. For instance, some academics have suggested that the GWT may be unable to explain the role that unconscious processing plays in memory consolidation (Hegarty, 2022). Moreover, the same author has written an entire thesis on the critique of the GWT.

Although not much was covered about this model here, I recommend reading literature on GWT independently. Since the GWT and its archnemesis, the Integrated Information Theory (IIT), are currently up for a tremendous scientific dispute spreading among academia, I believe there is enough information for an individual search. Moreover, considering that the GWT does not focus on memory specifically, it is not important to discuss it further within the scope of this paper, rather than limiting it to an outline.

Thus, GWT is still a well-known theory in cognitive research and has been used to explain a variety of cognitive processes, including attention, perception, and memory consolidation. The idea has the potential to influence the creation of new models and theories of cognitive processes by providing a framework for comprehending how conscious awareness develops from the integration of scattered information in the brain. The GWT offers a helpful foundation for understanding how memory consolidation works in the brain as a whole. The theory can help explain how information is transported from STM to LTM during the consolidation process by highlighting the function of the global workspace in combining data from various processing units. Yet, it has never been the memory model on its own and, as for 2024, has come under great fire from the IIT supporters (and vice versa), which are two of the main reasons for the in-depth explanation within this paper.

Memory Consolidation and Sleep Theories

In the 21st century, there is no doubt that memory consolidation is greatly aided by sleep (Klinzing et al., 2019). Sleep is defined as a natural and reversible state of reduced responsiveness to external stimuli and relative inactivity, accompanied by a loss of consciousness (Rasch & Born, 2013). Reduced sleep and disturbances lead to significant cognitive and emotional problems, which can aid and cause certain mental disorders (Brown, 2012). Sleep occurs at consistent intervals and is controlled by homeostasis, meaning that lack or postponement of sleep leads to a longer period of sleep afterward (Borb & Achermann, 1999). This signifies that the importance of sleep in relation to health cannot be diminished.

The brain consolidates newly generated memories and blends them with previously learned information while we sleep (Klinzing et al., 2019). Certain patterns of brain activity, including slow oscillations and sleep spindles, which serve to restructure and stabilize neural connections, support this consolidation process (Ackermann & Rasch, 2014). Various types of memory consolidation are linked to various sleep stages. Slow-wave sleep (SWS) is necessary for the consolidation of declarative memories, which include facts and events, whereas rapid eye movement (REM) sleep is crucial for the consolidation of emotional and procedural memories (Ackermann & Rasch, 2014). Memory performance can be significantly impacted by the quantity and quality of sleep. Lack of sleep has been proven to affect many memory functions, such as attention, working memory, and LTM (Alhola & Polo-Kantola, 2007). Persistent sleep issues, including insomnia or sleep apnea, can also prevent the consolidation of memories and result in cognitive deficiencies (Kitamura et al., 2020).

Overall, sufficient sleep is vital for learning and consolidating memories and is a crucial component of sustaining normal cognitive performance. Hence, given the aforementioned, it is clear that sleep and memory consolidation go hand in hand. Thus, it is important to talk about sleep and associated processes, as well as system consolidation theories that specifically address sleep and dreams. The next section will do exactly that by discussing the most

prominent sleep consolidation theories available to this day in the same manner as done in the previous sections.

The Two-Process Model of Sleep

The first model within this sleep consolidation is the Two-Process Model of Sleep (TPM). It is a widely accepted theory that proposes two primary processes governing sleep: the circadian process and the homeostatic process, making up for “sleep homeostasis” (A. A. Borbély, 1982). The TPM is primarily used to study the interaction between sleep and circadian rhythms in animals. According to this theory, since the homeostatic process is primarily responsible for memory consolidation, sleep is essential for memory consolidation (A. Borbély & Tobler, 2024).

The 24-hour circadian rhythm affects tiredness and alertness, and the circadian mechanism controls when and how long people stay awake (Reddy et al., 2024). On the other side, the homeostatic process controls how much sleep is required to preserve physiological and cognitive performance, with sleep pressure building up throughout time awake (Deboer, 2018). The TPM postulates that the homeostatic process is crucial in supporting memory consolidation and that it serves this role during sleep. In particular, the model contends that building up sleep pressure when awake increases the demand for sleep, which in turn improves the consolidation of memories created while awake (A. A. Borbély, 1982).

The term "sleep homeostasis" was coined to specify the regulated balance between sleep and waking. The regulatory homeostatic process was designated as "Process S". In the TPM, its interaction with the circadian pacemaker (process) "Process C" can account for sleep duration. Local, use-dependent slow-wave activity changes were demonstrated in humans by the selective, unilateral activation of a cortical region prior to sleep (Thomas et al., 2020). It involves the two processes S and C, which typically act in synergy and reinforce each other (A. Borbély & Tobler, 2024), see Figure 5.

Figure 5. The two-process model of sleep regulation. Illustration depicting the two-process model of sleep regulation. The level of Process S increases during wakefulness and decreases during sleep. Process C exhibits sinusoidal behavior, with the highest pressure to sleep occurring when the difference between the two is at its maximum, also known as the sleep gate. (Yang, 2013)

The model's duration of sleep is determined by the interaction of Process S with a threshold modulated by Process C. The model has been extended in 2024 to include the ultradian nonREM-REM sleep cycle, which includes the initial buildup of slow-wave activity within a nonREM sleep episode (A. Borbély & Tobler, 2024).

The TPM and its function in memory consolidation have been supported by a large body of research. For instance, one study discovered that sleep-dependent memory consolidation was strongest in the morning, when sleep pressure is at its peak, indicating that the buildup of sleep pressure plays a crucial part in memory consolidation (Stickgold, 2005). Another study confirmed that sleep is important for the consolidation of memories, finding that those who were sleep-deprived had decreased memory consolidation, outlining the importance of sleep homeostasis (Whitney et al., 2015). Additionally, studies have shown that the TPM may explain the various sleep stages and how they relate to memory consolidation. NREM sleep, which is mostly driven by the homeostatic process, has been found to promote the consolidation of declarative memories in contrast to REM sleep, which is primarily governed by the circadian process (Rasch & Born, 2008). The neurological mechanisms supporting the two-process model of sleep and memory consolidation have also been studied. For instance, one study discovered that sleep deprivation decreases activity in the hippocampus, a part of the brain that is essential for memory consolidation, indicating that the homeostatic process might aid memory consolidation by encouraging hippocampal activity while you sleep (Havekes & Abel, 2017).

The TPM and its presumptions regarding the connection between sleep and memory consolidation, however, have been contested by several studies. For example, some studies have discovered that sleep-dependent memory consolidation can happen even when there is no sleep pressure, indicating that there may be additional elements that affect memory consolidation while you sleep (Walker & Stickgold, 2004). As circadian disruptions have been demonstrated to hinder memory consolidation, other research has shown that the circadian process may be more important to memory consolidation than previously believed (Stickgold, 2005).

Overall, The TPM offers a helpful framework for comprehending how sleep and memory consolidation are related. It emphasizes the importance of sleep stages in memory consolidation and suggests the vital role of sleep as a homeostatic regulatory instrument. It is noteworthy to address that the author (A. A. Borbély) has been loyal to the model for decades now, with the latest update being published in 2024, emphasizing the relationship between the sleep stages and the brain's thermal regulation. Over these years, the TPM has gained significant recognition as the theoretical baseline. Although the model does not make bold and novel claims, majorly discussing conservative, well-established truths, its importance cannot be underestimated in the eyes of gradual but reliable knowledge construction. While there is still much to learn about the complex mechanisms underlying sleep-dependent memory consolidation, such as the relation to the organism's metabolic processes during the sleep stages, the TPM provides a valuable starting point for further, more in-depth, research in this area.

The Memory Reactivation Theory

Memory Reactivation Theory (MRT) is an explanation of how memory consolidation happens during sleep, introducing the process of memory reactivation (No specific author). According to this concept, the brain repeats and reactivates memories formed during waking when we sleep (Favila et al., 2020). This process reinforces these memories and integrates them into the brain's current knowledge networks. In this sense, the theory suggests that sleep plays an essential role in memory consolidation as a process during which the memories are reactivated to aid their consolidation.

It is also important to note that the process of memory reactivation has been found to be realistic as an integral aspect of the memory consolidation process over decades and is not considered a mere theory anymore, but rather a factual notion (Paller & Voss, 2004). Hence, similarly to the theory of General Memory Processing, the MRT has been widely accepted and now “circulates” within the scientific arena as the concept known as “memory reactivation” (Genzel et al., 2020); however, within the scope of this paper, it will be referred to as a theory (MRT), which it has been initially proposed as.

Firstly, the process by which previously encoded memories are restored to a state of accessibility or activation is referred to as memory reactivation (Genzel et al., 2020). This may transpire via a multitude of mechanisms, encompassing the provision of cues or signals that are linked to the initial encoding of the memory, and also during sleep (Paller & Voss, 2004). Reactivation of memories is frequently associated with memory consolidation, the stabilization and fortification of recently formed memories to prevent their forgetting (Paller & Voss, 2004).

By introducing the concept of memory reactivation, neuroscience seeks to comprehend the processes by which memories are modified, retrieved, and stored over time. It contributes significantly to the collective comprehension of memory processes and the neural mechanisms underlying them. Reactivation is linked to the formation of more robust memory traces and can transpire either during wakefulness or sleep (Favila et al., 2020). The ramifications of this phenomenon extend to learning, the development of long-term memory, and therapeutic approaches targeting memory-related disorders (Laurino et al., 2022).

Studies using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to analyze brain activity during sleep provide one of the most important pieces of evidence for the MRT. In one study (Debas et al., 2010), individuals were instructed to memorize a series of finger gestures while wearing an fMRI scanner. Researchers discovered that the same brain areas that were activated during the initial learning task were also active during sleep. This shows that the memory of the finger motions was reactivated during sleep, thereby enhancing the memory trace and increasing consolidation.

Studies examining the involvement of certain brain waves in the consolidation of memories during sleep provide more evidence in favor of the MRT. For instance, some research (Massimini et al., 2004) indicates that during NREM sleep, the brain produces slow electrical oscillations. It is believed that these oscillations serve an important role in memory consolidation by aiding the reactivation of memories formed while awake. In support of this theory, research has demonstrated that activating these slow oscillations during sleep can improve memory consolidation and subsequent test performance (Möller & Born, 2011). Such views are also supported by the findings examined within the section of the Two-Process

Model of Sleep, emphasizing the common idea of the importance of slow-wave sleep in memory consolidation. The one distinction is that TPM does not claim the importance of memory reactivation specifically during this sleep stage, whereas the MRT does, elaborating extensively on this process.

While empirical research has provided substantial support for the Memory Reactivation Theory, it does have several drawbacks. Because it is not possible to regulate the reactivation of individual memories during sleep, it is difficult to test the idea on humans in a controlled laboratory setting. In addition, some academics have questioned the generalizability of the theory, noting that it may not apply to all sorts of memories or to all people (Favila et al., 2020). Rather than that, the process of memory reactivation has been an integral aspect of sleep consolidation research, sometimes being denoted as the “key” to sleep consolidation.

MRT has also significant implications for our knowledge of memory consolidation and sleep despite these uncertainties. By emphasizing the significance of sleep in memory consolidation, the theory emphasizes the requirement of adequate, high-quality sleep for healthy cognitive functioning (similarly to the TPM). In addition, the idea posits that therapies focused on enhancing sleep quality or boosting the reactivation of memories during sleep (such as targeted brain stimulation) could have significant benefits for memory consolidation and cognitive performance, which has been found effective in the clinic practice (Arulchelvan & Vanneste, 2023).

The Memory Reactivation Theory, therefore, provides a strong foundation for comprehending how memory consolidation happens during sleep that has been significant in researching the underlying mechanisms of sleep and its effects on memory. By proposing that the brain actively reactivates memories during sleep and reinforces them through a number of methods, this theory has significant implications for our understanding of the cognitive benefits of sleep and the potential for therapies focused on enhancing memory consolidation. Although the theory has shortcomings, it has received substantial empirical support and continues to be an influential framework for comprehending the mechanisms behind memory consolidation.

The Sleep-Stage Memory Consolidation Theory

According to the Sleep-Stage Memory Consolidation Theory (SSCT) (Walker & Stickgold, 2006), different sleep phases have diverse effects on the consolidation of various types of memories. This theory postulates that memories formed when awake are originally retained in the hippocampus. Then, memory consolidation and integration take place in the neocortex during sleep when memories are gradually moved there from the hippocampus (Walker & Stickgold, 2006). This theory concentrates on the sleep component while technically discussing the memory hippocampal dependency proposed by the Standard Model or Multiple Trace Model.

The fact that memory consolidation seems to be most efficient during slow wave sleep (SWS), a stage of sleep characterized by slow, synchronized brain activity, is one of the fundamental discoveries that support SSCT (Born, 2010). According to studies, memory recall is positively connected with how much SWS a person experiences after learning. For instance, a study (Rasch et al., 2007) discovered that after learning word pairings, participants who received more SWS had higher memory recall than those who received less SWS.

Rapid eye movement (REM) sleep is another sleep stage that is thought to contribute to the consolidation of memories. The brain is extremely active during REM sleep, which starts about 90 minutes after falling asleep and is marked by fast eye movements and vivid dreams (Dang-Vu et al., 2010). It is believed that REM sleep is used to consolidate emotional memories (Rho et al., 2023). Research has revealed that REM sleep improves the retention of emotional memories and that the amygdala, a component of the brain responsible for processing emotions, is more active during REM sleep (van der Helm & Walker, 2011).

There is evidence to support the notion that other sleep stages, in addition to SWS and REM sleep, may contribute to memory consolidation. For instance, research by Backhaus et al. provides evidence that different sleep stages may contribute to memory consolidation. For instance, one study (Backhaus et al., 2008) discovered a favorable correlation between memory retention in a verbal learning task and the number of sleep spindles, short bursts of brain activity that happen during non-REM sleep.

Although the SSCT has gained a lot of empirical support, it has certain drawbacks as well. For instance, it's not entirely known how memories are transported from the hippocampus to the neocortex when we sleep or how several sleep stages might work together to enhance memory consolidation. However, considering the fact that such limitation is present in the vast majority of sleep and memory consolidation theories, it can be thought of more as a fundamental unanswered question rather than a mere flaw in a specific model's explanation. Furthermore, it is unclear if the same mechanisms that enable memory consolidation while you sleep also help other types of learning and memory, like the development of motor skills (Walker et al., 2003). However, certain inroads are made in human fMRI scans in this direction with the potential to resolve this question as well.

Despite the aforementioned drawbacks, SSCT has significant ramifications for our understanding of how sleep affects memory consolidation and could actually help improve memory retention. For instance, as a means of increasing memory consolidation during particular periods of sleep, researchers have started to investigate the use of targeted memory reactivation (Whitmore et al., 2022), a method that entails introducing sounds or odors that were associated with learning while awake. The idea also emphasizes the significance of receiving enough sleep for the best memory performance and contends that elements that disturb sleep, such as sleep disorders or specific drugs, may harm memory consolidation.

Thus, SSCT offers a framework for comprehending the function of several sleep stages in memory consolidation, has extensive scientific support (Backhaus et al., 2008; van der Helm & Walker, 2011; Whitmore et al., 2022), and has significant implications for both fundamental research and real-world applications (Whitmore et al., 2022). The model has already offered helpful insights into the connection between sleep and memory, even if further investigation is necessary to completely grasp the mechanisms behind sleep-related memory consolidation.

Memory Reorganization Theory

According to the Memory Reorganization Theory (MRT), in order to increase memory consolidation and retrieval, our memories are ordered and reconstructed during sleep and waking. Memories are dynamic rather than static, and memory reorganization is crucial for LTM preservation as well as memory consolidation.

The hippocampus, a part of the brain important for the development of LTMs, is where new memories are originally stored, in accordance with MRT. These memories are rehearsed and solidified in the cortex, the outer layer of the brain in charge of higher cognitive tasks, both during sleep and during waking. In order to improve the stability and accessibility of memories and consequently consolidate them, neuronal connections between cortical neurons are strengthened and reorganized during the memory consolidation process.

The proposition that sleep is essential for memory consolidation is one of the main components of MRT. The brain can concentrate on strengthening memories while it is largely free from sensory input during sleep. Several types of memories, including declarative, procedural, and spatial memories, have been demonstrated to be better consolidated during sleep. For instance, a study indicated that sleeping after mastering a new motor skill resulted in much better skill performance than staying awake (Rasch & Born, 2013).

The notion that memory consolidation is an active process involving memory reactivation and remodeling is a crucial component of the MRT. Sleep allows the brain to consolidate and integrate new information into existing memory networks by “replaying” newly learned memories, which can also explain the phenomenon of visual dreams as a by-product of memory reorganization. However, MRT does not focus on the process of dreaming much, mentioning it vaguely. Both rapid REM and NREM sleep are assumed to be when memories are reactivated and reorganized, but the precise mechanisms by which this happens are still unclear (Rasch & Born, 2013).

According to MRT, memory reorganization can take place when a person is awake, especially during times of rest or quiet (lesser sensory input). The brain can actively reorganize memories at these times by updating inaccurate or out-of-date memories and combining new knowledge with previously acquired knowledge. For instance, a study (Wamsley & Stickgold, 2011) discovered that sleeping after mastering a novel fact-based memory exercise resulted in a stronger incorporation of the new material than waking up.

The investigation of memory retrieval has also made use of MRT. This theory contends that memory retrieval entails the reactivation and reorganization of memory traces, which are impacted by emotional and environmental signals. For instance, one study (Bowen et al., 2019) discovered that emotional context signals during retrieval boosted the reactivation and consolidation of emotional memories.

The study on the treatment of memory problems, including Alzheimer's disease and PTSD, is often linked to MRT. According to research, sleep problems are widespread in both PTSD and Alzheimer's disease (Delic et al., 2021), which can impair memory function by interfering with the process of memory reorganization during consolidation. In order to create new treatments for these disorders that concentrate on memory consolidation and retrieval, it may be helpful to understand the mechanisms behind memory reorganization throughout sleep and waking.

While MRT offers an insightful framework for comprehending how memories are consolidated while we sleep, it is not without its drawbacks and detractors. One criticism is that the theory may not adequately account for the consolidation of other sorts of memories, such as procedural memories, or memories for skills and habits, as it primarily focuses on declarative memories or memories for facts and events. The idea has also come under fire for failing to take into consideration how emotional arousal affects how memories are formed when we sleep.

Moreover, several studies that support the notion have yielded contradictory findings. In contrast to the theory's presumption that consolidation during sleep is more effective for firmly encoded memories, a study (Rasch & Born, 2008) indicated that memory reactivation during sleep was more effective for weakly encoded memories than strongly encoded memories. Another study (Wilhelm et al., 2020) challenged the theory's assertion that memory reactivation is an essential mechanism for consolidation by finding that memory reactivation did not improve memory retention in humans.

The Memory Reorganization Theory may be oversimplified, according to some experts, and additional systems may be involved in the consolidation of memories while we sleep (Moscovitch & Gilboa, 2022). For instance, some research has suggested that memory consolidation may be greatly aided by sleep spindles, or short spikes in brain activity during NREM sleep (Mander et al., 2011), which has not been discussed within the notion of MRT. Additional research has suggested that the default network of the brain, a network of brain areas active during rest and daydreaming, may also be involved in the consolidation of memories while you sleep (William Domhoff, 2011).

MRT, then, is a cognitive theory that highlights the dynamic nature of memory as well as the significance of memory reactivation and rearrangement for memory consolidation and retrieval. According to this theory, memory reorganization occurs most effectively during sleep and awake, and memory consolidation is an active process that entails the strengthening and reorganization of neural connections. The theory has also gotten a lot of credit and support (Bowen et al., 2019; Delic et al., 2021; Rasch & Born, 2013; Wamsley & Stickgold, 2011). This idea has significant implications for comprehending the neurological basis of memory and creating new treatments for memory problems, even though the mechanisms driving memory reorganization are not yet fully known. MRT continues to be a useful framework for comprehending the role of sleep in memory consolidation despite numerous drawbacks and objections (Mander et al., 2011; Moscovitch & Gilboa, 2022; Rasch & Born, 2008; Wilhelm et al., 2020; William Domhoff, 2011). The mechanisms enabling memory consolidation during sleep are not entirely understood, and it is unclear to what extent the MRT adequately captures these mechanisms.

Discussion

We first discuss the Theory of the General Memory Process, which proposes that memory consists of three general cognitive processes: memory encoding, storage, and retrieval, which are the three main general memory processes widely recognized in the scientific community. However, as previously explained, other processes such as memory consolidation are also vital to successful memory formation. The Multi-Store model states that when information is read by sensory organs, it is first recorded in the sensory memory store. If an individual attends to the stimulus, information is then transferred to the STM, and if the information is elaborately rehearsed, it is then allocated linearly to the LTM. Thus, the idea of memory consolidation in this model is supported by the fact that there is a process of rehearsal that helps the transfer of information from STM to LTM. The LPM is another memory model that describes memory recall for stimuli as a function of the depth of mental processing. According to this theory, there is only one type of memory, and the ability to remember depends on the depth of information processing. All in all, these models build up the theoretical base that is necessary for an advanced understanding of memory consolidation. Although the Multiple-Store model and The LPM contradict each other, they all consider and allow for such processes as memory

consolidation. That said, both universal models acknowledge the existence of memory consolidation.

We next discuss modern memory consolidation theories that are widely accepted and have substantial evidence. One such theory is the Cognitive Schema Theory, which is a cognition framework that explains how people utilize mental schemas to process, organize, and integrate information. According to the theory, people construct cognitive schemas via their experiences, and these schemas direct their perceptions, thoughts, and behaviors. According to the CST, people interpret and make sense of the world around them using their cognitive schemas. The CST contends that a person's pre-existing cognitive schemas — which direct the acquisition and retrieval of new information — have an impact on memory consolidation. The Standard Model is one of the most tested theories in memory consolidation. The model states that STMs are initially encoded and stored in the hippocampus before being gradually transferred and consolidated to long-term storage in the neocortex and decaying from the hippocampus. The Complementary Learning Systems (CLS) theory, on the other hand, posits that the brain contains two different learning systems, the hippocampus and the neocortex, which collaborate to develop and preserve memories. The hippocampus, which is in charge of STM, analyses and consolidates new information before sending it to the neocortex, which maintains LTM. Multiple Trace Theory (MTT) was proposed as an alternative to the Standard Model. It states that whenever information is presented to a person, it is encoded as a unique memory trace composed of a combination of attributes. Moreover, MTT builds on the distinction between semantic and episodic memory and addresses some limitations of the Standard Model with a focus on hippocampal dependence. Unlike the Standard Model, this framework distinguishes between semantic and episodic memory as they rely on two different memory systems. When episodic information is encoded, there are semantic aspects of that specific memory that will be encoded additionally. Thus, like SMM, MTT has a number of evidence and counter-evidence studies. However, for complete justification or disproof of the theory, there is still a lot of investigation needed.

We next discuss newer memory consolidation theories that are not yet well supported and may lack sufficient evidence for their justification or lack thereof. One such is the Trace Transformation Theory (TTT), which is a cognitive theory that provides a novel strategy for memory consolidation by positing that experiences are not transferred from the hippocampus to the neocortex but rather changed within the hippocampus itself into LTMs. On the other hand, a cognitive theory known as Competitive Trace Theory (CTT) posits that memories compete with one another for access to constrained brain resources. CTT suggests a novel method of memory consolidation in which the strongest memories are kept and the weaker ones are lost. According to CTT, several brain pathways are simultaneously activated when we experience anything. The strongest pathway is the only one that is preserved as a memory because not all paths are equally powerful. The MeshCODE theory is another newer cognitive theory, which states that memory is organized based on a hierarchical network of categories, with more general categories at the top and more specific categories at the bottom. Each concept is represented by a unique code, which includes the codes of its parent categories, forming a MESH (Memory, Encoding, and Storage Hierarchy) code. According to the MeshCODE theory, memory retrieval is facilitated by the similarity between the cues used to retrieve a memory and the codes used to store that memory. In addition, this theory suggests that memory is stored not only in the brain but also in the environment. Another relatively new theory called the Global Workspace Theory (GWT) aims to explain how awareness develops within the brain. One area where the GWT has been successfully used is memory consolidation. The theory has been used in particular to explain how data is moved during consolidation from

STM to LTM. According to the GWT, the prefrontal cortex and parietal cortex are two examples of specialized brain regions where STM is largely processed. These modules are in charge of short-term information storage and manipulation, but they rarely result in long-term adjustments to neural connections.

Finally, we discuss the sleep-related theories of memory consolidation, as sleep is essential in the consolidation of memories. The first theory is the Two-Process Model of Sleep, which is a widely accepted theory that proposes two primary processes governing sleep: the circadian process and the homeostatic process. The Two-Process Model of Sleep postulates that the homeostatic process is crucial in supporting memory consolidation and that it serves this role during sleep. In particular, the model contends that building up sleep pressure when awake increases the demand for sleep, which in turn improves the consolidation of memories created while awake. The next theory is the Memory Reactivation Theory, which states that the brain repeats and reactivates memories formed during waking when we sleep. This process reinforces these memories and integrates them into the brain's current knowledge networks. According to the Sleep-Stage Memory Consolidation Theory, different sleep phases have diverse effects on the consolidation of various types of memories. This theory postulates that memories formed when awake are originally retained in the hippocampus. Memory consolidation and integration take place in the neocortex during sleep when memories are gradually moved there from the hippocampus. This theory concentrates on the sleep component while technically discussing the memory hippocampal dependency like the Standard Model or Multiple Trace Model. According to the Memory Reorganization Theory, a cognitive theory, in order to increase memory consolidation and retrieval, our memories are ordered and reconstructed during sleep and waking. This theory suggests that memories are dynamic rather than static, and memory remodeling is crucial for LTM preservation as well as memory consolidation. The hippocampus is where new memories are originally stored, in accordance with the Memory Reorganization Theory. These memories are rehearsed and solidified in the cortex, the outer layer of the brain in charge of higher cognitive tasks, both during sleep and during waking. In order to improve the stability and accessibility of memories and consequently consolidate them, neuronal connections between cortical neurons are strengthened and reorganized during the memory consolidation process. The assumption that sleep is essential for memory consolidation is one of the main components of the Memory Reorganization Theory. The brain can concentrate on strengthening memories while it is largely free from sensory input during sleep. Several types of memories, including declarative, procedural, and spatial memories, have been demonstrated to be better consolidated during sleep.

Here, we have presented a summary and comparison of multiple theories surrounding memory consolidation. While not all theories that have been suggested are covered, we have included those that are currently widely accepted or are beginning to receive more attention and traction. There is a definite need for further research to be done into the process of memory consolidation, both in wakefulness and sleep. Overall, the main objective of this paper is to provide new and prospective scientists with an insight into current memory consolidation theories and their relevance, as well as account for newer and less well-known models that offer different perspectives.

Conclusion

This paper has reviewed 15 different memory consolidation theories that describe and explain the process of memory consolidation from the system's point of view or refer to it through

specific aspects of memory consolidation like sleep or hippocampal dependence. Each theory was provided with an explanation of its history and context, strengths and supporting evidence, weaknesses, limitations, and a general conclusion. Despite some of the theories not giving sufficient evidence in the face of relevant studies, the main purpose of this paper was to introduce all the abovementioned theories to a wider public to allow for alternative viewpoint comparison and general theories' understanding in a shorter format, which was accomplished. Besides, there are still other areas related to memory consolidation worth discussion like memory consolidation and specific genotypes or synaptic aspects of memory consolidation, which would be useful additions for further research.

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